

What is an ugly car? A grounded theory approach on a webpage's comments

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Abstract In automotive design, the misuse of some aesthetic variables such as proportion, symmetry or balances etc. during the aesthetic design process can produce a negative aesthetic response to the user such as, when people assess a car as ugly. However, there is not a systematic study about the elements which actually affect the aesthetics of a car and not even theories to aid the car's designers in this process. Thus, we applied a Grounded Theory methodology using as data source a Yahoo blog "10 ugliest cars of all time" to obtain a first approach about how people understand and perceive ugliness in a car. We found five hypotheses about how people make an aesthetic assessment of vehicles, which were faced with the aesthetic theories to confirm the results obtained.

Keywords Car, Ugliness, Grounded theory, Aesthetics, Design

Introduction

During a production run of four years the Pontiac Aztek, see Figure 1, commonly "derided as ugly", only sold 108,500 units; it was a huge flop for Pontiac Aztek (Elliott, 2010). Comments about its aesthetics were merciless:

"The Aztek is the only car that I can remember that people would walk by and actually point and laugh at you when you were driving it, (...) people would giggle and point because it was so hideous looking." (Jake Fisher, Consumer Reports).

Let us consider two fundamental assumptions for this paper based on common knowledge: the first on ugly as an aesthetic assessment and the second on the opposition beauty-ugliness.

First assumption: ugly as an Aesthetic Assessment (AEA)

When we make an AEA, of something, "ugly" is a possible result. AEA in product and automotive design is very important because it allows companies to design more competitive products with aesthetics geared to a population segment of consumers; the attention of the users is attracted by good aesthetics which fills their needs and fulfill their most important values and aspirations (da Silva et al 2013; Dell'Era, Verganti 2007; Crilly et al. 2004; Crilly et al 2009, Crilly, 2010). Chinese producers are the largest manufacturers in the world by the number of cars produced each year. Their aesthetic design is improving every year. Consequently, people's AEA on vehicles of Western carmakers will be even more demanding in the future.

We make many AEA through our daily lives; however little is known scientifically about how we make them (Kozbelt & Kauffman, 2015). Our daily experience shows us that we make those assessments in a rather automatic and effortless way: they may result in quickly and spontaneously our (aesthetic) opinions on

Figure 1. Pontiac Aztek: an industrial flop due to its ugliness? But, what makes a car ugly? Photo: IFCAR [Public domain], via Wikimedia Commons

a certain matter. As psychological aesthetic constructs, they are affected by a lack of reliability: there is a disagreement between individuals when assessing an aesthetic artifact and the replication of results may be poor across multiple types of researches (Tinio & Smith, 2014). Also on the validity: when we say that something is "beautiful" or "ugly", what are we precisely evaluating in a product? A part of a product? The whole product? (Goodman, 1968) argued that artworks possess relatedness, and we believe that cars do too. This feature means that any particular aspect of them (color, contrast, delicate brush strokes) can be very relevant for the aesthetic experience.

Carrying out an aesthetic assessment in research one or many subjective or objective aspects can be measured (Kozbelt & Kauffman, 2015). Five subjective constructs are currently (Kozbelt & Kauffman, 2015): aesthetic sentiment, aesthetic experience, aesthetic judgment, aesthetic preference, and aesthetic pleasure. Two of the objective aspects considered are the indices of aesthetic achievement and, the characteristics of the artifact (i.e., Gestalt properties). Many other measurements are possible as well. For a review (Kozbelt & Kauffman, 2015). The question resulting from AEA is: Which are the terms or concepts related to AEAs on ugly cars?

Second assumption: the opposition ugliness-beauty

The second assumption is that we tend to use “ugliness” as a term opposed to “beauty”. However, one question that needs to be asked is: is ugliness the opposite of beauty? Or, is it a term opposed to something else? Could a theoretical overview of ugliness be able to answer this question? Therefore, we will present a theoretical overview of ugliness to examine existing accounts to resolve this question.

Historically, beauty has been one of the main concerns of aesthetics. The lack of an ugliness theory is noticeable. Many different approaches on ugliness have been developed through history. For instance, for Plato and Aristotle ugliness was simply the opposite of beauty. This powerful idea dominated aesthetics until the beginning of the 20th century: ugliness was something without an aesthetic value (Kuplen, 2013). In the “Aesthetic of ugliness” Rosenkrantz, (1853), described ugliness as an analogy with moral evil, this being the opposite of the good.

In line with seeing ugliness as the opposite to beauty, Eco (2007) compares the synonyms of beautiful (pretty, cute, pleasing attractive ...etc.) and ugly (repellent, horrible, horrendous, disgusting...etc.) to conclude that “whereas all the synonyms for beautiful could be conceived as a reaction of disinterested appreciation, almost all the synonyms for ugly contain a reaction of disgust, if not of violent repulsion, horror, or fear”. Hillman (1981) argues that the ugly creates more strong aesthetic responses than the beautiful. Hagman (2011) argues that ugliness is the traumatic disruption of an aesthetic experience; the formal qualities of the object turn out to be the origin “of the most repulsive and disgusting feelings”. P 7.

In psychological aesthetics, little is known of what ugliness constitutes. There are no consensual responses to two main questions: Is beautiful the opposite to ugly? Are ugliness and beauty opposed constructs? Stich (2004) suggests that beauty and ugliness are not two opposed poles along the same dimension but are “two independent dimensions”. According to her, aesthetic-affective responses consist of two orthogonal dimensions representing the response to ugly and beautiful objects. On the other hand, society and culture affect ugliness as well, for example, elegance and sophistication have been associated with higher classes, contrary to the lower ones where ugliness would be more common.

The diversity of concepts shown above, and the lack of theoretical links among them, shows an important gap in the field of the aesthetics of the ugly. Moreover, the absence of experimental or systematic observational works in this overview supports the view of the lack of an ugliness theory constructed on empirical grounds which makes it difficult to try to study the subject systematically. In conclusion, it is not clear if ugliness is the opposite of beauty or if it is a term opposed to something else.

The data: the webpage comments

The 10 ugliest cars ranking

In this paper, we are interested in how real people use the ugly term in their everyday life because we think that it is a first step understanding ugliness. An approach studying this would be studying people in their daily lives; however this is highly time-consuming. Incidentally, we came across a huge source of data concerning people’s comments about ugly cars made by the visitors of the Yahoo blog The 10 ugliest cars of all time, which in the last review on 05 November 2015 it contained 3968 comments. The list of the cars was created by Karl Brauer who has been in the automotive publishing industry for 20 years as CEO and editor in chief of TotalCarScore.com and Edmunds.com. The list is shown in Table 1, which includes similar rankings from other web-pages. Almost all the cars presented in those web-pages are from 1945 onwards. (Huffman, 2013) advances one reason for this:

“ (...) to 21st century eyes it’s tough to make judgments in the context of 75 or 85 years ago. And before that, the way a car looked was almost always determined solely by how its primitive parts bolted together. Design virtually didn’t exist.”

The cars presented are from any domestic car category: sedans, SUVs, MPVs, compacts, etc. We believe that this increases the difficulty of the ranking task because different cars categories possess very different appearances, i.e., it would be easier to compare an SUV with an SUV than to compare an SUV with a sedan. We believe that this compromises the validity and reliability of those rankings. Table 1 shows a highly noticeable lack of coincidences among the rankings. The Pontiac Aztek is the most frequent car in the table (6 times), followed by the AMC Gremlin (1970-1978), 4 times, and the Fiat Multipla 1998 with 3 times. However, as a mitigating factor, it should be considered that the number of car models in the time period considered is over thousands. The ranking refers to a model of one specific year or for a time period between some years.

Characteristics of 10Ugliest blog comments

The blog allows posting comments (“posts”) by the page visitors. The comments are the opinions and thoughts of the visitors to the page; they are chronologically arranged (Jansen, 2008). The language used in these comments is considered less structured, more ambiguous and harder to understand than in well-formed texts (Jansen, 2008). The interaction among the page’s users, for instance, feedback through thumbs up or down icon, was not considered.

All of the comments contained in the blog are a rich and free source of readily available data focused on the subject of the ugly car. However, in this case, we cannot ensure that all comments are serious opinions or thoughts. It is clear that some of them are funny or made for teasing.

This blog was chosen because it allows the posting of unrestricted spontaneous or thoughtful comments by

the visitors, who do not have, necessarily, knowledge of cars, assuring that any person can comment. However, probably, amateurs on cars or other opinion leaders on car styling could post comments about the subject too.

The research problem depends on how to take advantage of this low structured data to find out some determinants of the ugliness of a car. We believe that a multifaceted problem such as ugliness requires an exploratory and open-ended method approach capable of identifying its components, even if they are of different levels. Moreover, to tackle this problem systematically, the research objectives must cover the individual, the artifact and the context where the aesthetic interaction is carried out. Thus, the main question of this paper is: which concepts or terms are related to the ugly and ugliness comments on cars? And how are those concepts related?

Hence, the research objective is to identify new-concepts and categories making up probable determinants of ugliness and to develop hypothesis and insights worthy of being researched systematically further. This is why we used a grounded theory approach.

The remaining of this paper is structured as follows: In section 2, the method and the used procedure are described. In section 3 the results of the analysis are presented in tables containing the categories and examples obtained from the comments. Finally, in the point 3.F, some hypotheses were formulated which are discussed in section 4.

Method

The grounded theory approach: its conceptual basis

Grounded Theory (GT) is an inductive general research methodology (Glaser & Strauss, 1967) which is based on data collected in the words and actions of those

individuals under study (Goulding, et al. 2005) p 29. The theory may thus be generated initially from the data and it evolves along the research through interplay of data collection and analysis (Strauss & Corbin, 1994). Instead of an exhaustive literature review of ugliness before entering into the field, the developing theory makes the researcher focus on relevant literature, where the grounded concepts emerge (Goulding, et al. 2005). However, GT would be specially adapted to address ugliness if we consider the fact that aesthetic literature on ugliness is rare and even rarer in product design.

A misconception of GT is that the researcher should go into the field not knowing of any theory related to the phenomenon, though; this would favor that the theory emerges essentially from the data (Goulding, et al. 2005). Nevertheless, what is required is that the core categories emerge in a delicate balance between drawing on the researcher's reading and life experiences while keeping an open mind about the concepts emerging from the data (Goulding, et al. 2005).

The GT was chosen for this study because; first it allows the creation of theoretical categories from the review of poorly structured data, such our case, in a systematic, agile and flexible way. Second, it allows research on the world of real users which is not biased by any experimental conditions or requirements, and this without a preconceived hypothesis (Glaser & Strauss, 1971). In other words, it would allow the formulation of a clear hypothesis in order to understand the reasons of why a person considers a car as ugly. Third, concerning the data source, in GT the researchers must look for events in a representative community of the phenomenon and the interactions where the phenomenon is expressed. One must look for the people who are most likely to provide pertinent information (Goulding, et al., 2005). This is exactly the case of a specialized internet page with comments, which is accepted as a common source of data in GT (Strauss & Corbin, 1994).

Table 1. Ranking ugliest cars.

	10 Ugliest Cars of All Time - CNBC.com/ Yahoo! Cars	The World's Ugliest Cars. Bloomberg Businessweek	Top 10 Ugliest Cars Ever - RM AutoBuzz	10 of the world's ugliest cars - Telegraph	100 Ugliest Cars of All Time Edmunds.com
1	Mercury Zephyr 1978	Chevrolet Chevette	Porsche Panamera 2010-present	Jeep Cherokee 2014	Lamborghini Veneno 2014
2	Edsel Corsair 1958	Ford Edsel	Ford Granada 1975-1980	Pontiac Aztek 2001-2005	Lincoln Versailles 1977
3	Pontiac Trans Sport 1990	AMC Matador	Ford Fairlane 1957-1959	Yaris Verso	Acura ZDX 2010
4	Aston Martin Lagonda 1982	Chevrolet Corvair	Nissan Cube 2009-2014	Fiat Multipla	Cadillac Deville 1985
5	AMC Marlin 1965	AMC Gremlin	Hyundai Tiburon 2000-2001	Subaru Impreza 2000	Pontiac Aztek 2001
6	Pontiac Aztek 2001	Chevrolet Vega	Chevrolet Malibu Maxx 2004-2007	Mini Cooper Paceman	Fiat Multipla 1998
7	Plymouth Valiant 1960	Pontiac Aztek	AMC Gremlin 1970-1978	Ford Scorpio	Datsun F10 1974
8	Isuzu VehiCross 1999	Ford Pinto	Lincoln Continental Mark VI 1980 - 1981	SsangYong Rodius	Edsel 1958
9	Isuzu Axiom 2002	Yugo	Pontiac Aztek 2001 - 2005	BMW X6	Bristol Blenheim 1976
10	AMC Gremlin 1970	AMC Pacer	Davis D-2 Divan 1948	Subaru Tribeca	BMW 7 Series 2002

Figure 2. GT process.

Procedure

The technique of theory generation was applied from textual data (Strauss & Corbin, 1994). Firstly, Data collection should be coded according to an established family of codes, then the coding data is organized into categories named Core Categories, secondly the data is re-categorized to obtain more accurate information, into a second level of categories called category 2.0, with the objective to find concepts that would be Thirdly, where the information comes from, in GT the researchers must look for events in a representative community of the phenomenon and the interactions where the phenomenon is expressed, see Figure 2. One must look for the people who are most likely to provide pertinent information (Goulding, et al, 2005). This is exactly the case of the comments on a specialized internet page, which is accepted as a common source of data in GT (Strauss & Corbin, 1994) the basis for some Theoretical Reflections, which lead to a final hypothesis.

In GT once the researcher starts codifying the data, the codes are used to look for the presence of data belonging to those codes iteratively. There is a continuous interplay between data and codification. The result of the adapted methodology is a convergent-divergent process where the data is constantly compared iteratively, allowing to obtain information to finally formulate the theory.

A — Data

The data must be collected from the original sources using the original language and expressions of the people, without any alteration.

B — Family Code

This stage starts by assigning codes for the raw data using Computer Assisted Qualitative Data Analysis Software. Each comment of the text must be taken, line by line, and named according to some *families codes* previously defined. (These are defined by the researcher)

C — Core Category

Once all the comments are clustered in *family codes*, it is necessary to compare the codes according to perceived similar patterns, a higher level of abstraction; these categories are then grouped into

Figure 3. Detailed GT process.

more precise categories which finally make up the *core categories*.

D — Category 2.0

When the *core categories* are established and the first categorization is made a second categorization is made by similarity with the topics of the first categorization until a saturation point is reached, i.e., when the researcher does not find further new information or elements.

E — Concepts

The comments contained in the *categorization 2.0* should be analyzed this building concepts that meet the main ideas (Pre-hypothesis), which later will allow doing theoretical reflections.

F — Theoretical reflections

At this point, hypotheses are formulated according to the *core categories* and the thoughts about the concepts obtained in the previous point.

Results

The method used here will be explained in detail point by point below. See Figure 3.

A — Data recollection

The data was collected from the comments of 10Ugliest blog webpage, where people gave their opinion about the list of the 10 ugliest cars presented by the webpage’s author. There were 6039 comments in 539 pages.

B — Family Code

The analysis starts by assigning codes for the raw data used. Each comment of the text was taken, line by line, and codified according to the *family codes* that we defined before to start the review of the comments (Brand car’s, Aesthetic appreciation and Extra qualities) see *Table 2. Family Code*. The codification was made until reaching a saturation point.

C — Core Category

Once the comments were encoded into the three family codes. We made a new categorization based on comments patrons of the topics contained in those

family codes such as, aesthetics, emotions, memories, functionality and semantic symbols see Figure 5. This led us to arrive at two core categories which covered and enclosed the main topics of the new categories: (i) User Experience (UX) which is constituted for three levels, aesthetic, meaning and emotional, make up the user experience (Hekkert & Schifferstein 2008). The aesthetic level is associated with the “product’s capacity to delight one or more of our sensory modalities” (Hekkert & Leder 2008). The emotional experiences, are those “typically considered in emotion psychology and in everyday language about emotions, such love or anger, which are elicited by the appraised relational meaning of products” (Desmet & Hekkert, 2007) and the meaning level is “the ability to assign personality or other expressive characteristics and to assess the personal or symbolic significance of products”. , (ii) Functionality, it is related to the performance of vehicles. Some examples of the new categorization and the comments contained there are shown in *Table 3. Core Category*.

Table 2. Family Code.

Family code	Explanation	Example
Amc Gremlin, Aston Martin Lagonda, Edsel Corsair, Isuzu Axiom, Isuzu Vehicross, Mercury Zephyr, Pontiac Aztek, Pontiac Trans sport, Pymouth Valiant, Amc Marlin.	codes refer to the brand of the car mentioned	Comment: “the Marlin was already outdated, too big, and AMC was a brand with a reputation for mechanical failings. By then, only self-abusers or the clueless would buy AMC”. Code: AMC Marlin
Aesthetic appreciation: Beautiful, Ugly	This category was determined according to the perceived appreciation (positive or negative) of each comment	Comment: “I think the AMC Marlin is a sweet looking ride. Throw a nice paint job and some wicked rims. PERFECT!!!” Code: Beautiful Comment: “Also rather than the Valient, I would have certainly considered the ugliness of extreme boredom that was the visual design of the Aspen” Code: Ugly
Extra qualities	Refers to non-aesthetic qualities.	Comment: “I loved my Gremlin. It was a great running car with good economy. A perfect second car” Code: Extra qualities

Table 3. Core Category.

Core Categories referring to UX, Aesthetic level: <i>Aesthetic, shape, color, positive perception, negative perception</i> .		
UX: Aesthetics	Explanation	Example
Negative perception	If a comment contain negative appreciations of cognitive nature.	“The Edsel was actually referred to as the “toilet seat” in its time due to the horrible shape of its grill”
Core Categories referring to UX, Semantic level: <i>Model, Semantic</i>		
UX: Semantic	Explanation	Example
Semantic	Semantic, symbols, values, expressive elements	“You say ugly, to some I say classic.”
Core Categories referring to UX, Emotion level: <i>Emotion</i>		
UX: Emotion	Explanation	Example
Emotion	Emotions, Feelings, moods	“I’m surprised the Nissan Cube isn’t on this list. Too bad Pontiac is gone though, my first car was a Pontiac Grand Am, and then I traded it for a Sunfire-best car I’ve had so far.”
Core Categories referring to Functionality		
Component	Any physical component or part of the car	“I bought a 1958 Edsel Corsair after college in 1968. Low mileage, excellent condition and very cheap price.”

D — Categories 2.0

After the first categorization in the previous point, a second categorization was made. This emerged after having analyzed the comments contained in the point of core categorization and was found to have similarities in some topics, which drove us to make a new categorization until the point of saturation. See *Table 4. Category 2.0*. Here we form more precise categories.

E — Concepts

Using the comments contained in the categorization 2.0, some concepts were deduced. These correspond to the main idea which explained a phenomenon enclosed in each of the categories see *Table 4. Concepts*. They are presented as Pre-hypothesis which later will allow the making of theoretical reflections. Some of them are shown below. See *Table 5. Concepts*.

F — Theoretical reflection

By using the Core categories which comprise the two main topics extracted from the categorization process (UX and Functionality), some hypotheses were formulated to answer our questions: Which terms or concepts are related to AEAs on ugly cars? And, how are they related? In an opposite way? These hypotheses are:

H1. There is a high attraction for classic, simple but unique and novel features in cars.

H2. People tend to make emotional assessments, based on previous experiences with cars.

H3. People make positive AEAs when cars have exaggerated shapes or uncommon colors but preserve certain characteristics of their time.

H4. People make negative AEAs when there is not a consistency in shapes, colors and quantity of elements of a vehicle, generating imbalance in their whole.

H5. People make positive AEAs if they have had good experiences with functional characteristics of the cars.

Discussion

Based on the GT results, we can highlight that for ordinary people (without specialized knowledge in automotive design or aesthetics) ugliness is not understood as the opposite of beauty as we postulated at the introduction. Conversely, we identified that people use the two levels of the UX, and functionality of the car, as base concepts to make an AEA, where aesthetics is seen just as a fraction of the ugly concept.

Table 4. Categories 2.0.

Core Categories referring to UX in categorization 2.0, Aesthetic Level:

Analogies to compare, Color attribute, Car's Shape, Aesthetic positive preference, Aesthetic negative preference, Styles

Categories 2.0	Explanation of the comments	Example
The shape of the cars	About the shape and materials of vehicle.	"How the Honda Element and that other squared looking car with small tyres"
Aesthetic negative Preference	People make negative aesthetic assessments of the vehicles.	"The ugliest car, is the Lincoln Navigator, or the Cadillac Escalade, Terrible design, horrible"

Core Categories referring to UX in categorization 2.0, Semantic Level: *Adjectives*

Categories 2.0	Explanation of the comments	Example
Adjectives	People using adjectives to do aesthetics assessment.	"I loved my Gremlin, It was sport, sexy and had tons of room in the hatchback"

Core Categories referring to UX in categorization 2.0, Emotion Level: *Emotion- feeling*

Categories 2.0	Explanation of the comments	Example
Emotion – feeling	Related with expressed memories about their cars or emotions that it evokes. I.e. related with their family, school, friends, youth and traveling.	"The gremlin, a car only the owner could love"

Core Categories Functionality: *Functional attribute*

Categories 2.0	Explanation of the comments	Example
Emotion	Emotions, Feelings, moods	"I'm surprised the Nissan Cube isn't on this list. Too bad Pontiac is gone though, my first car was a Pontiac Grand Am, and then I traded it for a Sunfire-best car I've had so far."

Core Categories referring to Functionality: *Functional attribute*

Categories 2.0	Explanation of the comments	Example
Functional attribute	Related to the operation of the vehicles.	"The Edsel, actually incorporated some ingenious innovations such as a as a headlight that tracked along with the steering, among other"

Table 5. Concepts.

UX-Category: Emotion and Memories	
Concept:	Example
People associate good memories with the function, quality, performance and durability of the vehicle.	"I loved my Gremlin. I was fun, fast and handled very well. I learned how to really "DRIVE" a car with my Gremlin. I learned how to do 360's on wet pavement and that saved me and my family years later by avoiding a serious accident. My kids thought I was a stunt driver. It cost \$ 2200.00, got 27 mile to the gallon and was reliable. Mine was a 72, before they started to ruin the styling. If you never have one, you can't really talk about them."
Having good memories of the vehicles does not ensure a positive aesthetic assessment.	"My best friend in high school had a Gremlin. We called it the high top sneaker. Places in the floor board were rusted out, so you had to watch where you put your feet. Ugly car, but it holds great memories. We laughed our butts off in that thing"
Aesthetic assessments of vehicles are part of people's memories	"Oh come on Yahoo, The Mercury Zephyr was my first car. How dare you call it Ugly!
People evaluating the vehicles, attribute sentiments as boring or love	"Y absolutely LOVED my Aztec"
UX-Category: Shape	
Concept:	Example
An AEA related with heavy and big looking shapes.	"The Marlin was already outdated, too big, and AMC was a brand with a reputation for mechanical failing. By then, only self-abusers or the clueless would buy AMC.
A negative assessment is related to not relating the different parts of the vehicles: bodywork and tyres size and interior and exterior of the car.	"How the Honda Element and that other squared looking car with small tires"
UX-Category: Analogies	
Concept:	Example
People use analogies to make negative aesthetic assessments. Using elements with a negative connotation to make reference to big shapes, weight, rectangle shapes, no fluent lines, size.	"The AMC pacer should have been on this list as it looked like an upside down fish bowl on wheels."
Negative analogies were used to evaluate the bodywork, lights and grill of the vehicle	"The edsel was actually referred to as the "toilet seat" in its time due to the horrible shape of its grill..."
Positive analogies were related to the functionalities over the aesthetic appearance of vehicles.	"They were real works horses, and practically indestructible"
People use analogies to make a negative AEA. Using elements with a negative connotation to make reference to big shapes, weight, rectangles shapes, no fluent lines, size.	"The AMC pacer should have been on this list as it looked like an upside down bowl on wheels"
UX-Category: Colour	
Concept:	Example
The colour in vehicles is an important aesthetic attribute to do a positive assessment but it is not a determinant.	"I thought the Matador looked pretty cool, if you got it with the right color schema."
People give attributes of cars by color paint. (I.e. sexy, classic, sporty)	"The Gremlin in the right color scheme with stripes was a sexy little car, which lended itself to customizing well, with a chopped top, it was WILD."
The color in vehicles is an important aesthetic attribute to make a positive assessment but it is not decisive for it.	"I thought the Matador looked pretty cool, if you got it with the right color schema"
UX-Category: Adjectives	
Concept:	Example
People use adjectives that are not related to the shape to make an aesthetic assessment as unique, classic, innovative, styling, simplistic, appealing.	"You say ugly, to some I say classic"
Negative assessment is related with the use of negative adjectives such as big, fat and grotesque.	"The Camaro on the other hand (which IS supposed to be beautiful) was beaten with an ugly stick several years ago. Fat, freaky, disproportionate, grotesque and more, why isn't IT ever attacked as being the truly ugly car it is???"

(part 1)

UX-Category: Style

Concept:	Example
Positive assessment is done by the style of the cars: Classic, exotic, sophisticated, futuristic, ahead of time.	"The Edsel was before its time. Ford should look at making a throwback/futuristic version. The grill, to me, is awesome."
Negative assessments are related with not adapted aesthetic tendencies.	"GM among others ruined a few models with the odd triangle shape redesigns in the 80's like the Olds Cutlass."

UX-Category: Positive aesthetic assessment

Concept:	Example
People generally do not use the word beauty to do aesthetics assessment.	"The Gremlin looked pretty good"
People do positive aesthetic assessment by using words: Cool, styling, pretty, awesome, sexy and spectacular.	"I think the Aston Martin Lagonda was one of the more spectacular cars ever constructed."

UX-Category: Negative aesthetic assessment

Concept:	Example
People use the word ugly to make negative AEA.	"If there is a definician for Butt ugly the AMC Pacer took first place."
People make comparisons between formal aspects of vehicles to make a negative aesthetic assessment.	"I can't believe the Chevy Aveo didn't make the list. That thing looks absolutely horrible. It's more painful than the Gremlin to look at."
The comfort and luxury in car designs affect the AEA.	"Most all of the automobiles since the advent of the first Ford Taurus have been super ugly, too damn small and uncomfortable"
People make AEA which is negative to current vehicles because designers do not include in the designs risky colors, textures and shapes, in the design.	"I prefer the old one's because time can change people's minds and what was outs of styles back then can be in style today. The newer "ugly" cars can't even make it 10 years without being nothing more than a melted ball of plastic"

Functionality-Category: Function

Concept:	Example
A positive assessment is related to the functionality of vehicles as performance, sound, power and fuel saving.	"Now, wait a minute. I bought a 1976 AMC Gremlin brand new and had it for seven years. Ran beautifully. The six-banger engine just kept going and going; never had a thing done to it in those seven years."
A negative assessment is associated with function of the stereo, transmission, power, quality, and buttons.	"The Falcon certainly needed to be on your Schidtyshst, as it was not only ugly, but also a mechanical Schidtboks, with bad engineering."

(part 2)

For example, from the UX semantic level, the AEAs performed by the participants of the web-page were related to symbolic values, associated with the trends and styles of each decade where there were shown to be a high attraction for classic, simple, unique and novel features. Also, people used analogies as a way to make negative assessments linking ugliness with objects or animals in a negative connotation, which according to Desmet & Hekkert, (2007) is a cognitive process used to "assess the personal or symbolic significance of products". We think that these assessments are the result of people's memories and a visceral response to characteristics of the product; this represents somehow a strong or light involvement with the product.

H2, on the emotional level, would reveal that people's appraisals are affected by previous experiences; those appraisals are expressed as love, pride, dislike or anger (Desmet & Hekkert, 2007). These are unique for each participant of the web-page and refer to an emotional response to the experience they had with the cars, which were finally expressed in this case as negative or positive AEAs.

At the aesthetic level, we found that people make AEAs by referring to colors, shapes, quantity of formal elements and the existence of coherence between of car's visual characteristics as stated by H4. Also evident was a preference for vehicles which combine novel features as exaggerated shapes or uncommon colors but keep typical characteristics as expressed H1. This description corresponds to the MAYA principle, Most Advanced Yet Acceptable (Hekkert et al. 2003); (Jodard, 1992). This principle has been used in automotive design as a way to balance the amount of novelty and typicality present in a new car to finally gain the preference of customers (Diels et al., 2013): "the most successful cars have the MAYA principle in correct balance (...)", Bayley (2012), p. 12. However, when an imbalance is evident in some of the aesthetics characteristics of cars, as happened with some cars included in the list, the AEA is affected, resulting in an ugly car. Clough (2010) argues that car beauty is related to "clean, fluid lines and good proportion", p. 54, minimalist shapes and elegance and simplicity. He also confirms these findings, since he affirms that an imbalance between the novel, the innovative, and the typical gives rise to negative

appreciations. Thus, we believe that a poor control of aesthetic variables and standards of beauty (Hekkert, Leder, 2008) in car design, such as Golden ratio, balance, MAYA or peak shift (preference for an exaggerated color or shape in products) (Hekkert & Leder, 2008) might affect the aesthetic perception of the users producing finally a negative AEA as stated in H3.

Lastly, the functionality aspects of the vehicles such as performance and fuel economy also influenced the AEA, as expressed in H5. People's main expectations of a car would be about its correct functionality, rather than on aesthetics (Jordan 2002). These results satisfy Jordan's pyramid model and Kano's model (Matzler & Hinterhuber, 1998): products must work correctly and if this does not happen, people will be very disappointed with the product. So, in this case, people who had a good experience with functional characteristics of the cars made a positive AEA. Conversely, people with a bad functional experience made a negative AEA.

These findings finally, allow us to have an approach as to how people define what an ugly car is. We propose something that will call levels of ugliness which are formed for the aesthetic, emotional and meaning levels of UX, and the functionality. Results suggest that people cannot separate the ugly concept from those ugliness levels to make a negative AEA. That is why people use the word ugly when in at least one of the levels of ugliness, displeasure is generated (negative experiences).

The results and subsequent hypothesis generated are the beginning of a greater project: we will apply other methods to the Ugly Cars data to find out more response elements to the ugliness issue and to offer guidelines to car and product designers to avoid that problem.

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